

Website Faculty Of Applied Science

Husam Talal Diab, Amjed Abdullah Abdh, Ali Abdullah, Jaafar Abdelwahab

¹ Department of Computer Science, Applied Science College, Taiz University, Taiz, Yemen.

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ABSTRACT

Thousands of students take the decision that will have the significant impact on the rest of their life. This decision will affect their career, earnings, and professional development. A university website is the first impression to represent university reputation. This project highlights the making process of the responsive university webpage by using WordPress Content Management System. As the use of technology by the current and next generation of students as well as their parents continues to grow, universities will need to utilize better, responsive and more easily navigable websites. An alumni registration form is also included on the university website to get the information of the student. The website designed by using WordPress Content Management System. WordPress is the most popular, free, search engine optimizer, user-friendly and open source content management system (CMS) which established on PHP and MySQL database. An alumni registration form is also included on the University website

1. Introduction:

A website is defined as a set of files and related resources that can be accessed over the World Wide Web Where these files and resources are organized and grouped under one domain name. Through the Website among documents, images, text, and other types of files, and the name of the Website does not indicate that it is located in a particular physical location; Where the website resides on what are known as web servers that are actually spread in different locations in the world, and the website can consist of a file (HTML) or thousands of related files. The website is accessed over the Internet using a browser The web available on the user's device, where he enters the website's URL into the browser's address bar to go to it, and in case the URL of a particular website is not known; It is possible to search for this site using one of the search engines on the Internet, It should be noted that the websites are owned by individuals, companies, or certain institutions, as well as managed by those entities..[1]

We will develop a website for the College of Applied Sciences, Taiz University, through which we can communicate information to faculty members and students, and it will provide many public services for the College of Applied Sciences, The website will contain a page of news, information and decisions related to the Deanship And it will contain another page about news, student activities and college events And another about the departments and

heads of departments and another page about the student's data, knowing the subject's marks, the average, and the fees paid and remaining. The guardian can also know the information about the student. problems that contributed to the development of the site not knowing the student in the college news delay material marks and rate in correction material therefore, faculty members will be given permission to upload material marks to the site directly the student's guardian's knowledge of the subject marks and what are the remaining fees for the student..[2]

2. Project importance:

View the issues and events announced by the university and the matters related to them personally and on their page.

- Submit an application for admission
- Review their classes and exam schedules.
- Request their documents.
- Manage their accounts.

Administrators and educators can:

- Enter the midterm and final grades for each student.
- Write notes to be displayed in the student's file.
- View classroom schedules.
- View the list of students who passed exams and who could not pass the exam.
- Send a private message to one student, a select group, or all the students in the class with just one click.
- Class-related information, such as the beginning and end of the term, days and times, and location..[3]

3. The general goal:

Is to provide the best services and by all modern technology methods to reach the future vision of the Deanship and achieve its mission to raise the name of the college and maintain this position.

Project goals:

- Follow the best ways to implement academic services to the fullest, in the fastest time and with the least effort.
- Providing all admission, registration, academic advising and everything that serves the student through the electronic portal of the college website easily and conveniently
- Provide all information about the college, its departments, and admission requirements.
- Providing academic guidance according to a scientific approach that is compatible with technical progress and helps in the smooth progress of study and achievement among students.
- Follow-up students academically until graduation from the university.

4.Relevance to the Department

It is the body that links the Deanship with the various categories of the university community, as it contributes to conveying the message of the Deanship of Admission and Registration by employing the latest technologies in clarifying the information in a simplified manner such as graphic design, and presenting a good image of the Deanship to the university community by covering the events and activities of the Deanship to serve the Deanship's vision and mission[4]

5.Literature Review:

Some studies have sought to identify the obstacles to the effective establishment of Sustainable development at universities, finding that higher education institutions still need To do Facilitate and display its data and research groups(Leal Filho Et al.,2017;Chaleta et al.,2021)and even into their strategic plans(Bieler and McKenize,2017;Stoian et al.,2021).

Studies of the visibility of the Agenda 2030 on university websites can offer a complementary perspective to such research. It is worth highlighting, however, that the scientific literature related to Web visibility is not extensive. The most notable studies to date have focused on the analysis of Web visibility in relation to specific areas such as politics or the application of SEO strategies in different sectors predominantly involving business websites [5]

Apart from such "webometric" research, in recent years, there have been various studies of SEO specific to the academic sphere. These studies have dealt with questions such as the application of SEO techniques to the dissemination of academic production (Codina, 2017; Shahzad et al., 2017), the

optimisation of academic articles in Google Scholar (Beel et al., 2009), the visibility of universities on academic social media platforms (French and Fagan, 2019; Gonzalez-Díaz et al., 2015) and the use of SEO in repositories or[6] academic journals. However, there are very few studies dealing specifically with SEO and the visibility of universities on search engines. One such study is by Giannakouloupoulos et al. (2019), who analyse the relationship between a university's academic excellence and its Web visibility. Most existing studies focus on specific areas, either geographically (Yalcin and Kilic, 2016) or thematically (Özkan et al., 2019).[7]

Another line of research in this area that has been given considerable attention in recent years is the search engine manipulation effect. This is a term coined by Epstein and Robertson (2015), who define it as the manipulative effect that search engines can exert on users, which is masked in such a way that users are unable to recognise that it is happening.[9]

We have done a study on a project about the Applied College in previous projects and what it contains and includes characteristics and developments to facilitate the administration and the educational staff in the college some effort and time and it was important and great achievement also and may preserve data and all the details about the students, even if this student has a period of Graduation from college, his data remains preserved..

But it also had some shortcomings, which push us to provide the best in our new project in the development of previous projects and the shortcomings in them, which have a great goal and a greater impact than improvement and development, and we always look at the bad side to plan for the best..

Among the stages and steps in building its development:

It was built on an advanced website, which helped every student to access any data and information anywhere and anytime with ease

Databases have been added and designed on the amounts of fees and amounts that are paid to the administration.

6.Contribution:

Contribute to the development of the educational system and provide all the data that students need in Yemen and between private and public universities.

Increasing our knowledge of such projects if we encounter them in our practical life.

Contribute to presenting a model design that can be used by the competent authorities.

Contribute to the development of scientific research for the university.[10]

7.Methodology:

There are many general models that the project proceeds step by step as shown in software engineering books in order to become a system of high quality and efficiency at the lowest possible cost and these models:

- Waterfall model.
- Evolutionary development.
- Iteration model.
- Prototype.

The initial form (prototype) has been selected for the following reasons:

- .easy to understand and simple manage.
- Average cost.
- Average quality.
- Provides time and effort to the team.
- avoid a Lot of problems that may occur during work.
- suitable in small and medium enterprises and even in large projects, because it allows you to return to the previous step, so that the nature of large projects need to be consolidated constantly to previous step.[11]

Budget Estimates

We price your website development according to the amount of work, like coding, content creation, and graphic design. Here's how it looks like

Website Design and Development (this covers every design and development step)	1,500\$
Website Hosting	\$35 per month
Website's Monthly Audit (this audit shows you traffic, bug corrections, navigational details, and more)	9\$ per month

Time Table

id	Task	Duration	Star	Finish	Time implements
1	DESIGN	15 days	2022/7/24	2022/8/8	
2	FORNT END	45 days	2022/8/9	2022/9/24	
3	BACK END	100 days	2022/9/25	2023/1/5	6 months
4	CHECK	20 days	2023/1/6	2023/1/27	

Final summary

The study came up with the design of a website to publish the results of students in the College of Applied Sciences so that it can provide the best services to students and be able to facilitate the procedures between the student and the college and the results, taking into account all the services that the site can provide to the student and access to better quality and make updates according to technology and keeping pace

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